

sulphoxide (25.62×10^{-2} l. mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹) with the observed rate constant (8.80×10^{-2} l. mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹) indicates such a steric inhibition of resonance.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the University Grants Commission for the award of a Junior Research Fellowship to one of them (P.J.).

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Preparation of 2, 6-Anhydro-L-Gulose

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Manuscript received 22 March 1978, revised 12 July 1979,
accepted 6 October 1979

1-Deoxy-Nitro-L-gulitol was prepared by a modification of the procedure of Sowden and Fischer¹. This was then anhydriized by pyrolysis to form a Carbohydrate Anhydronitroalcohol, 2,6-anhydro-1-deoxy-1-nitro-L-gulitol which is the optical isomer of the compound reported earlier². 2, 6 anhydro-1-deoxy-1-nitro-L-gulitol was then subjected to the Nef reaction with sulphuric acid to form 2, 6-Anhydro-L-Gulose.

Experimental

Anhydriization of 1-Deoxy-1-Nitro-L-Gulitol to 2,6-Anhydro-1-Deoxy-1-Nitro-L-Gulitol.

1-Deoxy-1-nitro-L-gulitol (10g) was heated in an oven at 90° for 16 hours. The product was dissolved by 95% ethanol by heating in a steam bath and then allowed to cool. 2, 6-Anhydro-1-deoxy-1-nitro-L-gulitol crystallised out (1.3 g.). The mother liquor was evaporated to a solid which on similar treatment as above, yielded another batch (0.8 g.) of the same product. M. P. 166° [α]_D = 8.7°. Anal. found, C=37.6%; H=5.80% and N=7.45%; Calc. for C₆H₁₁O₆N; C=37.3%; H=5.69% and N=7.2%.

Conversion of 2, 6-Anhydro-1-Deoxy-1-Nitro-L-Gulitol to 2, 6-Anhydro-L-Gulose.

2, 6-Anhydro-1-deoxy-1-nitro-L-gulitol (0.8 g.) was heated with (1:1) H₂SO₄ for 2 hours. The excess acid was neutralised with ion exchange resin. The resulting solution was concentrated and crystallised from 95% ethanol when 2, 6-anhydro-L-gulose (0.74 g.) separated out. M. p. 136°; Anal. found, C=44.70%, H=6.40%; calc. for C₆H₁₀O₅, C=44.44% and H=9.17%.

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Isolation and Identification of Pigments of the Flowers of *Clitoria ternatea*

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Manuscript received 2 January 1979, revised 25 May 1979,
accepted 6 October 1979

BOTH the blue and white parts of the fresh flowers (1.5 kg) of *Clitoria ternatea* (Leguminosae) were extracted separately with 1% methanolic HCl. From the extract of blue parts three compounds A, B and C were isolated but the extract of white parts furnished only compound C in reasonable yield. The isolation of these compounds were done by paper chromatography (descending) using 40×20 cm What man No. 1 filter papers and n-butanol : acetic acid ; water (4 : 1 : 5) as developing solvent. The R_f values were 0.21, 0.38 and 0.87 for A, B and C respectively. The strips with different bands were cut out and eluted with 95% ethanol. The eluates were concentrated under reduced pressure and purified by precipitating with petroleum ether and repeated crystallisations.

The dark red compound A, C₂₇H₃₁O₁₆Cl (250 mg), gave all the colour tests of anthocyanins. On hydrolysis with 20% HCl, it yielded glucose (mp, mmp, chromatography and osazone) and an aglycone which was identified as cyanidine chloride by colour reactions, alkali degradation and UV spectral analysis in presence of specific reagents^{1,2,3}. Finally, the identity of compound A with cyanin chloride was established by direct comparison (UV, PC) with the authentic sample obtained from red roses.

Compound B (28 mg) was also recognised to be an anthocyanin from colour tests. Its structural studies could not be done due to paucity of the material.

The yellow compound C (175 mg), C₁₅H₁₀O₆, m.p. 277°, was found to be a flavonol. It formed a tetraacetate, m.p. 116°. The positions of hydroxy groups were settled to be 3,5,7 and 4' by colour reactions, degradation studies and spectral analysis. Thus the structure of C was established as 3,5,7, and 4'-tetrahydroxy flavone i.e., kaempferol, which was further confirmed by co-chromatography with authentic sample obtained from blue delphinium flowers.

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